

Methodology for Evaluating the Introduction of Traceability in Practice

1 Background

Research has shown that traceability has various advantages such as helping to understand the system, support maintenance activities and facilitate change impact analysis. For traceability to be established in practice having a tool alone is not enough. The tool also needs to be integrated into the development process and the links created need to be purposed in a sense that they are useful. In this study, we will investigate how traceability can be introduced in a company. We will first identify the objectives of the company with regards to traceability and tailor a solution (tool and process) that will fulfill these objectives. We will introduce this solution and investigate how the objectives of the company have been achieved, focusing on the advantages brought about by traceability.

2 Purpose of the study

The aim of the study is to investigate a transition towards using traceability in an industrial product development environment. We will investigate how the traceability activities (e.g., creation, maintenance, use) impact the development process. We will also investigate how a traceability management tool can be tailored to ensure cost-effective traceability. The research is guided by three research questions:

- RQ1** How can traceability be introduced to a specific project in an industrial development environment?
- RQ2** What are the short-term and long-term effects of using traceability in a development effort?
- RQ3** What are the costs of introducing traceability in an industrial development process and what is the ROI?

Particularly, a number of questions related to changes in the development process and the business environment will be investigated by the study to address the research questions:

1. What are the traceability goals for the company? (RQ1)
2. What traceability information model is suitable for the development environment? (RQ1)
3. What is the traceability process suitable for the development environment? (RQ1)
4. What kind of development activities does traceability support? (RQ2)

5. What kind of business activities does traceability support? (RQ2)
6. What is the cost of establishing traceability in a development organization? (RQ3)
7. What are the benefits of establishing traceability? (RQ3)
8. How do these benefits compare to the cost of establishing traceability? (RQ3)

3 Environment

The case study method will be used to evaluate the introduction of traceability in a company that develops in-house software. The case study will focus on a project that does not have any traceability links.

The project is a website for customer relationship management, developed mostly in PHP. The developers use PHPStorm¹ for coding. The modeling takes place in Papyrus within the Eclipse IDE. So far, models have been exported so developers can view them.

4 Method

The first step in the study are interviews that allow understanding the concrete purposes of traceability links in the project and which stakeholders are involved. Metrics will be defined based on the purposes to understand whether these goals have been achieved. A baseline for these metrics will be measured before traceability is introduced and compared to measurements after the introduction to understand how the development team's performance has changed.

Based on a definition of the traceability purposes, a traceability information model will be created to define the semantics of the traceability links. We will then customize Eclipse Capra to the project and educate the developers in its use.

The developers working on the project will then start creating and using traceability links while observed and coached by us for one to two days. We will then conduct interviews with developers to get their opinion on the tools and process of creating traceability links directly after their introduction. The developers will then use the links for a short time (a week may be?) and conduct another interview with them on the use of trace links. The aim here is to find out what the short-term benefits of traceability are (if any).

The study will follow the steps below, taken and extended from Rempel et al. [2]. Steps that have already been completed are marked with a reference to the corresponding section in this document. They have been re-ordered to fit the purposes of this study and extended to include measurements on different time scales. Short-term benefits and developer attitudes will be assessed directly after introducing the traceability practices into the project. To investigate the mid- and long-term effects of traceability practices, we will revisit the company after a certain period of time. A mid-term evaluation will be done after one month by

¹ <https://www.jetbrains.com/phpstorm/>

interviewing the developers about adoption of the practices and the effects that can be seen. After an additional five months, the interviews will be repeated. This will allow us to investigate if traceability practices were taken up by the developers and if they are useful in practice. This long-term perspective can also help us identify changes in the process that allows the development team to work with traceability more efficiently.

1. Analyze the existing software development process
 - 1.1 Identify actors in software development process (cf. Section 5)
 - 1.2 Gather goals and tasks of actors (cf. Section 5)
 - 1.3 Derive conceptual goal model of the software process (cf. Section 5)
 - 1.4 Identify which metrics are available in the company to measure the process quality (added)
 - 1.5 Measure the current cost (in terms of effort/time) of making a change without having traceability links (added)
2. Identify traceability usage goals
 - 2.1 Identify the traceability purposes of the company and which concrete goals they want to achieve through interviews* (cf. Section 6)
 - 2.2 Develop conceptual goal model for traceability usage (cf. 6)
3. Identify and Assess Existing Trace paths(cf. Section 7)
 - 3.1 Identify traceable artifacts (cf. Section 7.1)
 - 3.2 Identify trace paths (cf. Section 7.4)
 - 3.3 Create the traceability information model together with the company and implement it in the tool (cf. Section 7.4)
 - 3.4 Asses conceptual traceability information model – Detect ambiguous artifacts, detect volatile traces, detect trace path duplicates
4. Assess suitability of traceability usage goals
 - 4.1 Assess traceability information model against traceability usage goals (cf. Section 8)
 - 4.2 Detect missing trace paths
 - 4.3 Detect superfluous trace paths
5. Asses suitability of existing trace paths
 - 5.1 Assess traceability usage goals against software process goals
 - 5.2 Detect missing traceability goals
 - 5.3 Detect superfluous traceability goals
6. Deployment of the Traceability Solution
 - 6.1 The company selects a project that will be used for the study
 - 6.2 Customize the traceability tool for the project (with the elicited information model)
 - 6.3 Educate developers about the traceability tool and the practices
 - 6.4 Introduce traceability links to the project
7. Evaluation of the short-term Effects of the Traceability Solution
 - 7.1 Interview developers on the process of creating traceability links
 - 7.2 Continue development in the presence of traceability links (one week)
 - 7.3 Interview the developers on the process and how traceability fits in
 - 7.4 Collect information on which development activities are improved by traceability and to what extent (short-term benefits)

8. Evaluation of the mid- and long-term Effects of the Traceability Solution
 - 8.1 Continue development in the presence of traceability links (1 month)
 - 8.2 Interview the developers on the process and how traceability fits in
 - 8.3 Collect information on which development activities are improved by traceability and to what extent (mid-term benefits)
 - 8.4 Continue development in the presence of traceability links (5 months)
 - 8.5 Interview the developers on the process and how traceability fits in
 - 8.6 Collect information on which development activities are improved by traceability and to what extent (long-term benefits)
 - 8.7 Define the ROI by calculating the cost/effort of establishing and maintaining traceability links and measure the benefit in effort reduction

5 Software Development Process at the Company

5.1 Old Process

The company works in an agile way and uses Scrum as their agile method. As the scrum methodology instructs, the company has product owner, scrum master, developer and quality engineer (tester) roles in the team. However in some cases one person can have more than one role. For example the lead developer also acts as a scrum master. The role of the product owner is also not centralized in the team but there is one product owner for the company and sub-product owners who take charge of sub-projects within the bigger project (comprising of the website, marketing and CRM). Since the company develops a website, there are two more roles, that of a copy writer and art designer. The copy writer is responsible for the text that goes on the website while the art designers create art work like logos and icons for the website.

5.2 New Process

The company works in an agile way and uses Scrum as their agile method. As the scrum methodology instructs, the company has product owner, scrum master, developer and quality engineer (tester) roles in the team.

In eyeOpen case, the development team is an horizontal group of developers distributed on different value teams. A value team is a group of people from different expertises (development, marketing, operations) that work together to achieve a defined goal. eyeOpen consists of 4 value teams that are depicted in the Figure 1. Each team has dedicated developers that will contribute to implement features to achieve the team's goal. In detail:

- **Operations Team** wants to increase the efficiency of the Operations department (advisors, mid-office, COO); their focus is the automation of advice and mid-office tasks and the improvement of the eyeOpen partnerships and commercial offer.

- **SQL Team** – where SQL stands for Sales-Qualified Team – aims to increase the number of warm leads, which are the ones that will end up in buying a house and, hence, closing a mortgage with eyeOpen; their focus is the communication area, from the landing pages that depict eyeOpen services to the blog posts that explain different stages of the mortgage process and requirements.
- **Execution-Only Team** works to create the best execution-only customer journey, which differs from the advice-based customer journey by avoiding a direct talk with advisors and could aim to narrowing the gap between customer and moneylenders; their focus is to enhance the customer journey by requiring only necessary information, to improve the underlying business logic, and to refine the document handling process using the national mortgage data exchange standard.
- **Analytics Team** focuses on analyzing the performance of the company, under every aspect – sales, website visitors, advices successfully closed –, by extracting and processing useful data from Customer Module, Google Analytics, CRM, and other company-related resources.

Each team works autonomously and organizes itself in the agile Scrum fashion. Each of them has a Scrum Master that ensures that the Scrum principles are correctly applied and helps the team members to get over obstacles in that way. Each team has also its own Product Owner, depicted with a dark green box in Figure 1, who is responsible to define the team direction by deciding what is the scope of each sprint, in order to achieve the defined goal. Given the reduced number of dev resources, it might be possible that some of the development members can be assigned to tasks belonging to different teams.

The roles and the responsibilities of the roles are summarized in table 1.

Sprints last for two weeks and at the beginning of these two weeks a planning meeting is held to decide on which tasks need to be accomplished in the sprint and to assign the tasks to responsible developers. Every morning during the sprint, the team has a stand-up meeting. The sprint ends with a retrospective meeting to reflect on how the sprint went and find things that can be improved with the process.

Furthermore, at each sprint iteration, the Team Product Owners gather to coordinate the overall direction and to analyze which steps should taken further in the roadmap, by identifying high business value issues.

Role	Responsibility
Lead Developer / now product owner	Decides who is going to do what Makes an estimation of the story points Pushes the team to follow agile principles
Product Owner	Manages the different areas like the website and CRM and marketing Decides what should be done/creates specifications for the product together with sub-product owners
Scrum master	(Not visible) Pushes the team to follow agile principles
Developers	Implement features (write code) for back-end, front-end and CRM parts
Business Analyst	Specify requirements Analyze complexity of requirements Provide specifications to developers (only for business logic-related projects)
Project Manager (Not a role any more)	Get input for the product from all interested stakeholders
QA Engineer	Make a test plan Test features in the product
Copy Writers (now called Content Marketers)	Write copy Go through the system to see if the right copy was used
Art Designers (Includes Web-designer)	Create art artifacts for the front end of the website
Agile coach	Helps the Advisors teams to adapt to the Agile principles
Digitalization Program Manager	Identifies process tasks that might be implemented with software solutions.
Video Marketer	Designs and generates video content for both informing the customer and promoting the company mission.
UI/UX Designer	Creates prototypes for customer interaction and visual models for the customer journey.
Web Analyst	Control reports and dashboards, collects data and makes recommendations based on actual findings.
Customer Intelligence Analyst	Performs analyses and coordinate the development of divisional business plans by monitoring business performance against plan, and providing recommendations based on results.

Table 1: Roles and Responsibilities in the development process

Old Process	New Process
<i>Teams</i> Marketing, Operations, Development	Marketing, Operations, Digitalization, Analytics
<i>Product Owner</i> One central product owner and sub product owners for the sub projects	Dedicated product owner who also acts as a team leader for each team
<i>Developers</i> All developers with in one team and they work on task as they come in. No specialization to a specific product part	Developers belong to separate teams and concentrate on parts of the product relevant for that department. In case of lack of resources in one team developers from other teams can be borrowed

Fig. 1. New Organization Structure

6 Traceability Purposes

The second step in the process suggested in Section 4 is to determine the concrete traceability usage goals. According to the Grand Challenges of Traceability, all traceability efforts should be *purposed* [1]. Therefore, the concrete traceability goals of EyeOpen have been identified using interviews conducted in February 2017. The business analyst and the lead developer participated in semi-structured interviews. The interviews were transcribed and the transcription

was coded by two of the participating researchers. From the coded transcript, traceability goals were extracted. The Goal/Question/Metric approach [3] was used to formulate relevant goals and find metrics that can be used to measure whether the goals have been achieved. An overview of the identified goals can be found in Table 2 to Table 7. The data sources to which access is required are listed in Table 8.

Table 2: Goal/Question/Metric to identify traceability goals and metrics

Goal 1:	Increase the awareness of stakeholders about product changes from the business analyst point of view.
Rationale:	Different stakeholders are involved in the development of new features. Ideally, these stakeholders are able to shape the requirement as well as the implementation according to their needs. They also need to be aware of the schedule for the development of new features and give input for their prioritisation. Traceability can help to identify all the stakeholders concerned with a change early in the process by identifying which artifacts are connected to a change and from the artifacts identify which stakeholders (people who develop or use the artifact) should be involved.
Caveat:	It is not clear that this purpose can be achieved with traceability between development artifacts.
Question 1:	How easy is it for relevant stakeholders to influence the changes?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of comments on JIRA tickets from non-developers (analysis of JIRA tickets) – Number of suggested changes to JIRA tickets by developers (analysis of JIRA tickets)
Question 2:	To what degree are relevant stakeholders aware of the changes?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Likert Scale awareness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – not aware at all; 5 – very aware per task (Questionnaire with BA)
Question 3:	How timely are announced changes deployed?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Difference between time of announcement and time of deployment (analysis of JIRA tickets)

Table 3: Goal/Question/Metric to identify traceability goals and metrics

Goal 2:	Improve the visibility of the decision rationale from the development team’s perspective
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Rationale:	The rationale behind a requirement is important information for the development team since it can help make decisions during design, implementation, and test. As such, the rationale should be visible and understandable to the team. If the team understood the task clearly, it should require less discussion and less rework. Traceability links can support this purpose by connecting the relevant artifacts describing the rationale of decisions to the requirement description. NOTE: For a few delicate projects (e.g., the ones that have to follow certain standards) rationales are recorded in a separate document
Caveat:	It is not clear that this purpose can be achieved with traceability between development artifacts. However, we are going to test if traceability links can support understandability of the rationale.
Question 1:	How understandable is the decision rationale?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Likert scale understandability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – not understandable at all 5 – very understandable per task (Questionnaire with developers) – Numbers of traceability links per task (analysis of traceability model and JIRA tasks) – Correlation between number of traceability links and the understandability of the rationale (derived) – Number of re-opened tickets (analysis of JIRA tickets) – Number of rejected tickets (analysis of JIRA tickets) – Number of comments per task (analysis of JIRA tickets) – Correlation between number of comments and understandability rating (derived)
Question 2:	To what degree is the decision rationale visible to the team?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Likert scale visibility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – not visible at all 5 – very visible per task (Questionnaire with developers)

Table 4: Goal/Question/Metric to identify traceability goals and metrics

Goal 3: Improve the accuracy of effort estimations for tasks from the Lead Developer’s point of view.

Rationale:	One of the main tasks for the lead developer is to estimate the effort a certain implementation task is going to have. This has a major influence on the sprint and on the schedule for the developers since it essentially determines how many tasks the team will tackle during a sprint and how much time they can devote to each task. Increasing the accuracy of the effort estimation is therefore a goal. Traceability links can support this goal by providing insight into dependencies between artifacts and requirements, and by helping to identify which parts of the code have to be touched for a change. Since an estimation can never be 100% accurate, an additional dimension is how confident the lead developer feels with his estimations. If traceability links do in fact support the estimation, the lead developer should become more confident in estimating over time and the high confidence estimation should become more accurate at the same time.
Question 1:	How much does the estimated effort differ from the actual effort?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Average number of tasks per sprint (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Average number of deviating tasks per spring (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Percentage of deviating tasks per sprint (derived) – Initial estimation for each task in story points (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Updated estimation for each task in story points (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Average increase/decrease in effort per task (derived) – Number of JIRA comments about effort per task (analysis of JIRA tickets)
Question 2:	How confident is the lead developer in the estimation of tasks?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Likert scale confidence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – not confident at all 5 – very confident – Number of low confidence tasks that required a change (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Number of high confidence tasks that required a change (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets)

Table 5: Goal/Question/Metric to identify traceability goals and metrics

Goal 4:	Increase the efficiency of identifying artifacts relevant to a change from the developers' point of view.
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Goal 5:	Increase the efficiency of identifying artifacts relevant to a change from the business analyst's point of view.
Rationale:	<p>These two goals are closely related and only differ in the viewpoint. Therefore, they are treated together and the questions and the metrics are valid for both.</p> <p>At the moment, it is a significant effort to identify all artifacts that are affected by a change. The business analyst creates an initial change impact analysis, but that does not contain the code. The developers thus need to identify the relevant code parts themselves. Therefore, there is effort for both roles. If traceability links are established between all relevant artifacts, this effort should be significantly reduced and the information recorded for use in the future.</p>
Question 1:	How well are the different artifacts connected to the code?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of identified code sections per task (Analysis of traceability model and JIRA tickets) – Number of tasks (analysis of JIRA tickets) – Average number of identified code sections per task (derived) – Number of missed sections (analysis of commits)
Question 2:	How easy is it to identify artifacts connected to a change for a given task?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Likert scale difficulty of identifying artifacts connected to a task <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – very difficult 5 – very easy per task (Questionnaire with developers), (Questionnaire with business analyst) – Number of artifacts added after initial change impact analysis (analysis of traceability model and JIRA tickets)
Question 3:	How efficient is the creation of the change impact analysis?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Initial estimation for each task in story points (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Updated estimation for each task in story points (analysis of Product Backlog/JIRA tickets) – Average increase/decrease in effort per task (derived) – Duration of creating a CIA (time sheet of BA) – Effort of changing an existing CIA (time sheet of BA)

Table 6: Goal/Question/Metric to identify traceability goals and metrics

Goal 6:	Improve the visibility of the dependencies of the process steps from the lead developer’s point of view
Rationale:	Hidden dependencies are a major source of added effort. If dependencies are not detected during the planning process, they can become evident when code is checked in (in the form of merge conflicts), when it is compiled (in the form of failed tests or builds), or during design. Traceability links can help identify dependencies and thus, a system with a high number of traceability links should be less susceptible to this kind of mistake.
Question 1:	How often do dependency conflicts manifest in development?
Metrics:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Likert scale ease of dependency identification <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – very difficult 5 – very easy per task (Questionnaire with lead developer) – Number of merge conflicts (analysis of commit history, continuous integration server) – Number of backed-out patches (analysis of commit history) – Number of JIRA comments about dependency issues (analysis of JIRA tickets) – Number of failed builds (build history on continuous integration server) – Number of failed tests (build history on continuous integration server)

Table 7: Goal/Question/Metric to identify traceability goals and metrics

Goal 7:	Improve the visibility of progress from the Product Owner’s point of view
Rationale:	One of the stated goals, in particular of the lead developer, was to use traceability information to get an insight into the current progress of the development. The business analyst also emphasised the importance of having insight into the “entire lifecycle of a feature” and to get insights at all stages of the process. This kind of progress tracking is connected to traceability since traceability links allow, e.g., to identify if all relevant code segments have already been touched or to see if the relevant artifacts have already been updated.
Question 1:	How easy is it to gauge the progress of a task?

- Metrics:
- Likert scale visibility of progress
 - 1 – very opaque
 - 5 – very visible
 per task
 (Questionnaire with Product Owner)
 - Number of traceability links per task (analysis of traceability model and JIRA tickets)
 - Correlation of visibility and number of links (derived)
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Source	Comment
JIRA tickets	The JIRA tickets represent the epics and tasks and contain all relevant information about the implementation of a change. In particular, they contain traceability links to, e.g., commits and requirements documents and will contain the traceability visualisations done in Capra. The comments are a particularly valuable source of information and will be used to identify what the developers discussed while working on the task.
Product backlog	If a product backlog that is separate from the JIRA tickets exists, this can provide information about the estimation and prioritisation of tasks.
Commit history	Commit messages usually contain a link to the task they were intended for. They will allow us to see which code was changed to address which task.
Questionnaires	Qualitative data about the satisfaction of the different stakeholders is going to be collected with questionnaires.
Build history on continuous integration server	The build history gives insight into failed builds that can be caused by compile errors, failed tests, or dependency issues.
Time Sheets	All activities where effort is recorded will need to be accompanied by a time sheet. Since we can not expect developers to record all times accurately, this data collection tool will be limited to the BA.

Table 8: Data sources for metrics

7 Traceability Metamodel

7.1 Traceable Artifacts

From the interviews, a number of traceable artifacts have been identified. Their purpose, who works with them and how they are stored are detailed in the following.

Requirements: These are recorded as epics and epics are broken down into user stories. The product owner defines the requirements and documents them in a Google spreadsheet.

Model elements: UML models are used to create the architecture of the product (website and components it depends on). The business analyst creates these models using Papyrus UML.

PHP code: The code for the web product. The developers write this code and use PHP Storm as their IDE. The code is stored in a Git repository.

Unit tests: Tests for the product written in PHP as well. Tests are also stored in the Git repository together with the code. These tests are written by developers.

System tests: These are textual descriptions of the test that need to be performed manually on the product. They are written in Google spreadsheets by the QA engineer and also performed manually by the QA engineer.

Copy: These are textual content that go on the front end of the website. They are written and stored in Google spreadsheets.

Wire frames: These are designs /mock-ups on how the web pages will look like. They are created using a tool called Axure but the result is stored as an image attached in tickets in Jira.

Art designs: These are logos and pictures that end up on the web pages. They are also stored as attachments in Jira tickets.

Change Set: This is a PDF document that is sent by the regulator organization. It contains a list of changes in the standard that the company has to make. The BA receives this document and makes an analysis on which changes will affect the product.

Ticket: Requirements are broken down into epics or user stories. Regardless of the level of detail, these are always captured as tickets on Jira and assigned to developers there. Each ticket is created by the business analyst in collaboration with developers (was lead developer, now backend developer).

Wiki pages: These contain information on the product. Developers record information like how the system works and dependencies to third party library

Marketing assets/customer content: The marketing department produces documentation that they can use for their marketing tasks. These include, features offered by the company, prices and so on. These are stored electronically in wiki pages, blogs and checklists.

Road-map : This is a document that describes the plan for projects. It includes main tasks and milestones that need to be reached. Currently this is stored as a Google spreadsheet.

7.2 Existing Traceability Practices

Before introducing traceability in the company, we analyzed existing traceability practices that were already in place. This is to ensure that we can leverage the existing links and understand how these links can be integrated in to the new solution.

Currently traceability is done on JIRA tickets. Bigger features are defined as Epics in JIRA and within an epic, smaller tasks are defined. When the business analyst/product owner defines tasks tickets on JIRA, links to requirements, copy, wire frames, art designs, constants, code, other affected products and tests (not always) are created. These links can be made in the epic or if they are specific enough they can be added in the specific task. The aim is to make sure that the developer has enough information to carry out the task given. However, these links are transient as they are only valid for the current ticket/epic and for each task/epic that is defined the product owner/developer has to figure out which links should be established. The business analyst first identifies what needs to be changed, records this information in an excel file, creates tickets in JIRA from the excel file and add links to the tickets. If two tickets are related, a link is created between them by adding the ticket number of one ticket in the description of the other ticket.

To improve this current practice there is a need to have connections between requirements and other artifacts in the software and these connections should be reusable every time a change is requested.

7.3 Tool Chain

Fig. 2. Artifacts and their tools

7.4 Evolution of Traceability Metamodels

Fig. 3. Proposed Traceability Metamodel.

Fig. 4. Updated Traceability Metamodel. Links in red not supported by Capra but through JIRA.

Fig. 5. Updated Traceability Metamodel. Links in red not supported by Capra but through JIRA. Note that all development artifacts are now linked via the *Ticket*. The roadmap has been removed.

8 Evaluation of Traceability Metamodel Against Usage Goals

In this section, the traceability meta-model described in Section 7.4 will be evaluated in terms of the traceability goals that have been defined in Section 6. Whether these goals can be achieved or not depends on the expressiveness of the meta-model as well as the traceability practices that are put into place. In this section, we will only consider an evaluation of the meta-model, whereas the evaluation of the practices will be left to the empirical validation described elsewhere. Since we focus on the meta-model, the object of the analysis are the artifacts that are connected via traceability and the semantics of these links. The analysis here relates to the meta-model shown in Figure ??.

All links are undirected and establish 1:1 relationships between the artifacts. No additional information is captured in the links.

Support of goals The following list contains the goals and how the final version of the traceability meta-model helps to achieve them:

Traceability Goal 1: Increase the awareness of stakeholders about product changes from the business analyst point of view.

The traceability links and in particular the change impact analysis that is enabled through their existence allows the business analyst to communicate product changes to the stakeholders and to give an indication which impact they have. By including the CIA in the tickets, all stakeholders that have access to those get an immediate impression of the elements that are affected by the change.

Traceability Goal 2: Improve the visibility of the decision rationale from the development team’s perspective.

Links between requirements and tickets as well as between the roadmap and tickets indicate the rationale behind them.

Traceability Goal 3: Improve the accuracy of effort estimations for tasks from the Lead Developer’s point of view.

Links between the requirements and the model elements allow identifying all aspects of the system that are affected by a change. The transitive links to the implementation indicate the code elements that need to be changed.

This change impact analysis improves the overview and should support the Product Owner in estimating the task.

Traceability Goal 4: Increase the efficiency of identifying artifacts relevant to a change from the developers’ point of view.

This goal can be achieved due to the same reasoning as for Goal 3.

Traceability Goal 5: Increase the efficiency of identifying artifacts relevant to a change from the business analyst’s point of view.

This goal can be achieved due to the same reasoning as for Goal 3.

Traceability Goal 6: Improve the visibility of the dependencies of the process steps from the lead developer’s point of view.

The process steps correspond to different activities that need to be performed by different stakeholders. For instance, copy needs to be provided before the web page can be programmed. The existence of a traceability link between a requirement and copy thus indicates that the step has been done.

Traceability Goal 7: Improve the visibility of progress from the Product Owner’s point of view.

The traceability meta-model makes it easier to track progress since it clearly identifies the affected elements of the system that are affected by a change.

When comparing with which elements have already been changed (e.g., tests, customer content, models) to which have to be changed, a notion of completeness can be derived. Notably, however, traceability does not help establishing to which degree the different elements have already been completed, just if they have been touched at all.

Changes to the model due to evaluation The first revision of the analysis revealed that the concepts related to requirements were not clearly delineated. Since product changes impact the requirements and must be broken down to be recorded in JIRA tickets (Goal 1), it is essential that these are traced correctly. The first version of the model contained the concept of a “task”, however. This was ambiguous, since a task could be a user story or something more fine-grained. It was also ambiguous since the terms “ticket” and “task” were used interchangeably. For the purposes of traceability, however, the concept “ticket” is most suitable, since requirements (in the Excel document) will be linked to tickets in JIRA, no matter what level of abstraction they are.

This line of thought also revealed that traceability links that are maintained by Capra need to be distinguished from those maintained in JIRA. For instance, wireframes, copy, and art designs are going to be added to the JIRA ticket

as images or text, respectively. Therefore, the traceability link is going to be handled through the containment relationship in JIRA. Likewise, links between tickets (e.g., from an epic to user stories) are handled by JIRA. This has been made visible in the conceptual model.

Other than that, no obvious missing connections have been identified. It is not entirely clear if the links between tickets and implementation is necessary. Since the requirements are transitively linked to the implementation, it might not be helpful to have an additional link originating in the ticket. However, if commit messages are augmented with ticket numbers, this connection becomes relevant again and should be included. It can be helpful to determine progress (Goal 7).

9 Expected Outcomes

1. At the end of the study, we expect to be able to describe the development process of the company and how traceability activities (creation, maintenance, use) fit into the process. Figure 6 below illustrates this. We also expect to get information on the extent by which traceability links have an effect on the activities of the development process.
2. Information on the short-term and long-term benefits of traceability and in particular on how the attitudes towards traceability practices change and how the process and the way the tools are used evolve.
3. An estimate of the ROI of introducing traceability over longer periods of time, based on a measure of completeness. Hypothetically, the benefit of traceability links increases with the number of links that exist and with the parts of the system that are interconnected with traceability links. Therefore, as completeness increases, the teams' benefit should increase and thus the ROI.

Fig. 6. Integrating traceability activities with the development activities.

10 Questionnaire

The questions in this questionnaire are targeted for specific roles, as indicated in parentheses after each question:

- QA Engineer (QA)
- Product Owner (PO)
- Frontend Developer (FD)
- Backend Developer (BD)
- Business Analyst (BA)

1. When a change is requested, how easy is it for you to identify the stakeholders that should be informed of the change? (BA)

Very Hard Very Easy

2. When a change is made to the system, are all involved stakeholders aware of the change and how it impacts them? (BA)

Not aware at all Very aware

3. How understandable is the rationale behind the decisions about the software? (BD, FD, QA?)

Not understandable Very understandable

4. To what degree is the decision rationale visible to the team? (BA)

Not visible Very visible

5. How confident are you in estimation of tasks? (BD, BA, PO)

Not confident Very confident

6. How easy is it to identify artifacts connected to a change for a given task? (BD, FD, BA)

Very Hard Very Easy

7. How easy is it to identify dependencies between different process steps for a given task? (BD, FD)

Very Hard Very Easy

8. Given a specific task, how easy is it to gauge its progress and current status? (PO, BA?)

Very Hard Very Easy

11 Interview Questions to Gauge Short-term Benefits

In comparison to the questionnaire, an interview can give us insights into the practices and how the different parties use traceability links. While we can see whether or not they are perceived as useful from the questionnaire, the interview thus allows us to gauge why the usefulness is limited or which practices can be improved. Therefore, we pursue three goals with the interviews:

Goal 1: To find out how traceability practices fit in the process

Goal 3: To understand which traceability practices are performed and how

Goal 2: To elicit the short-term benefits of traceability

Interviews will be conducted with the people filling the roles listed below. Since some of these roles only consume traceability links while others produce and maintain them (indicated with an asterisk), some questions are not applicable to all roles and are marked accordingly.

- QA Engineer (QA)
- Product Owner (PO)
- Frontend Developer (FD)
- Backend Developer (*) (FD)
- Business Analyst (*) (BA)

1. What is your role in the company?
2. How long have you worked in this role?
3. Did you have any other role in this company?
4. Were you aware of the concept of traceability before the introduction by Paolo?
5. Do you create or use traceability links in your development activities? If yes:
 - 5.1 Which links do you create? (*)
 - 5.2 Which links do you use?
 - 5.3 For which purpose do you use them?
 - 5.4 Do you discuss the links with others in the team?
6. How do the current traceability links help to increase awareness of stakeholders that need to be notified in case of a change? (BA)
7. How do the current traceability links help to follow the rationale of decisions?
8. Do the current traceability links make you more confident when estimating the tasks? (PO, BA, BD)
9. How do the current traceability links help you to make better estimation of tasks? (PO, BA, BD)
10. How do the current traceability links increase your efficiency of identifying artifacts relevant for a change?
11. How do the current traceability links help you to identify dependencies between steps in the development process?
12. How do the current traceability links enable you to follow the progress of the task?

13. Do you see any other benefits associated with the links currently introduced?
If so, can you describe these benefits?
14. What is your opinion on the type of links currently present in the tool?
 - 14.1 Do the types make sense to you?
 - 14.2 Are there any more link types that you would like to have?
 - 14.3 Are there any link types that you find not useful?
15. Can you estimate how much effort it is to create traceability links for a change? (*)
16. What is your opinion on the effort of creating traceability links? (*)
17. Do you see the need to update existing traceability links? (*)
 - 17.1 When do you have to update the links? (*)
 - 17.2 How much effort is it to update the links? (*)
18. Now that the initial links are in place, when do you think will be the best time to create more links? (*)
19. Will the traceability links introduced change the way you work? For instance, do you need to communicate with more /less people?
20. Do you see any downsides associated with the links? If yes, can you describe these downsides?

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